

THE USE OF SOME THIOLACTIC ANILIDES IN INORGANIC ANALYSIS

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Six new thiolactic anilides were prepared and their usefulness in analysis was investigated. In most cases Ag, Pb, Hg^I, Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd, Bi, Sb, Fe^{III}, Ni, Co, Zn and molybdate were found to form complexes. Sensitivities for Ni and Co were found out. A nickel complex was analysed and found to contain two molecules of the reagent per atom of nickel.

Some thioglycollanilides have been used by us successfully in inorganic analysis (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 127). In the present work some new thiolactic anilides have been prepared and studied for the same purpose, with the hope that this series of reagents may prove to be more sensitive and useful than the corresponding thioglycollanilides by virtue of their higher molecular dimensions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiolactic anilides were prepared in a manner analogous to the preparation of the thioglycollanilides (*loc. cit.*). Equimolecular proportions of an aromatic amine and thiolactic acid were mixed in a 1" x 6" test tube and heated in a glycerine-bath maintained at 110°-120° for about 2 to 2½ hours in a slow current of CO₂. A solid was obtained when the melt was cooled or poured into a beaker of water. The lumps were crushed to powder in a mortar and washed with dilute HCl, and then with water to remove unchanged amine and thiolactic acid respectively. Further purification was made by repeated recrystallisations from dilute alcohol till the compound provided a constant melting point. They were then dried in a vacuum desiccator (H₂SO₄).

The amines used in the present work are aniline, *o*- and *p*-toluidines, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines. Table I records the m.p., analytical data and some properties of the thiolactic anilides.

TABLE I

Serial No.	Compound.	M.P.	% Sulphur.		Nature of the compounds.
			Found.	Calc.	
1.	Thiolactic anilide.	93°	17.59	17.67	White crystal; odourless; sparingly soluble in water, soluble in cold alcohol, acetone, ether, benzene.
2.	Thiolactic <i>o</i> -toluidide	122°	16.69	15.41	Do
3.	Thiolactic <i>p</i> - "	132°	15.65	16.41	"
4.	Thiolactic <i>o</i> -chloroanilide	91°	15.09	14.85	"
5.	Thiolactic <i>m</i> - "	83°	14.15	14.85	"
6.	Thiolactic <i>p</i> - "	115°	15.35	14.85	"

Use in Qualitative Analysis.—Ten drops of 1% alcoholic solution of a reagent was added to a test tube containing 2 c.c. of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of known p_H and 5 drops of molar salt solution. The resulting colour change or precipitation in cold or after heating on a water-bath was noted. In many cases the reagent itself came down due to dilution of the alcoholic solution, which was detected by disappearance of the precipitate in warm dilute alcohol. The salt solutions of Ag, Pb, Hg^I, Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd, Bi, As, Sb, Sn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al, Cr, Mn, Zn, Co, Ni, Ca, Ba, Sr, Mg, Li, Rb, Cs, Th, La, UO₂²⁺, MoO₄²⁻, WO₄²⁻ were used. Buffers of p_H 3.42, 4, 5 and 6 were prepared and used. For p_H 7, water, and for p_H more than 7, a mixture of NH₄Cl and NH₄OH, where possible, were used. Complete precipitation was qualitatively tested by digesting a salt solution with an excess of the reagent solution and testing for the absence of the cation or anion in the filtrate. The results of the tests are as follows.

Thiolactic anilide, at p_H 3.42-7, gave white precipitate with Hg^{II}, Cd, As, Sn and Ag at p_H 3.42-5 and Zn at p_H 4-7; grey precipitate with Hg^I, bluish violet with Cu, yellow with MoO₄²⁻; Ag at p_H 5-7, Bi at p_H 5-7 and Pb at p_H 6-7; greyish brown precipitate with Co at p_H 5-7, and brown with Ni at p_H 5-7. All the complexes were insoluble in water, and except the Cd-complex all were insoluble in cold dilute HNO₃ or dilute acetic acid. The molybdate complex was colloidal and on heating became soluble, developing a blue coloration probably due to reduction of Mo^{VI}. Complete precipitation was noted in case of silver. Nickel and cobalt gave voluminous precipitate in ammoniacal medium, but the precipitation was found to be incomplete even on digesting with a large excess of the reagent.

Thiolactic o-toluidide, at p_H 3.42-7, gave white precipitate with Hg^{II}, Cd, As, Sb, Sn and with Zn at p_H 5-6; yellow precipitate with Ag, Pb at p_H 5-7, Bi at p_H 4-6, and MoO₄²⁻ at p_H 4; grey precipitate with Hg^I, and Cu at p_H 3.42-4 and 7; greyish violet with Cu at p_H 5-6 and brown with Co and Ni at p_H 5-6 and in ammoniacal solution. Molybdate gave a blue coloration at p_H 5-7 on long standing. A temporary blue colour was observed with Fe at p_H 3.42-7 which quickly disappeared producing a white precipitate. The solubilities of the complexes resembled those of the corresponding complexes with thiolactic anilide. The iron complex (white) was soluble in dilute HCl or HNO₃ producing yellow solutions. Silver was completely precipitated from the solution at p_H 4.

Thiolactic p-toluidide, at p_H 3.42-7, gave white precipitates with Pb, Hg^{II}, Cd, Sb; yellow with Bi, MoO₄²⁻, Ag at p_H 4-7; grey with Hg^I, Cu at p_H 3.42; greyish violet with Cu at p_H 4-7; greyish brown with Co at p_H 5-7 and in ammoniacal solution; and brown with Ni at p_H 5-7 and in ammoniacal solution. With Fe, a temporary blue colour was observed at p_H 3.42-4 and 7, while at p_H 5-6 a reddish brown colour was obtained on addition of excess of the reagent solution. The solubilities of the precipitates were similar to the corresponding precipitates with the above reagent. Complete precipitation was noted in case of Ag, Cu and Bi at p_H 4.

Thiolactic o-chloroanilide, at p_H 3.42-7, gave white precipitate with Hg^{II}, Cd, Sb

and Zn at p_n 5-7; yellow with Ag and Pb at; p_n 5-6, MoO_4^{2-} and Bi at p_n 3.42-4; greyish violet with Cu; and at p_n 5-7 and in ammoniacal solution brown precipitate with Ni and Co. The colour of the nickel complex was more deep than that of the cobalt complex. The behaviour of the Fe and nature of the other complexes resemble those of the corresponding complexes of the above reagents.

Thiolactic m-chloroanilide, at p_n 3.42-7, gave white precipitate with Ag, Pb, Hg^{II} , Cd, As, Sb and Zn at p_n 4-7; yellow with MoO_4^{2-} , Bi at p_n 3.42-4; grey, with Hg^I ; greyish violet with Cu; and at p_n 5-6 and in ammoniacal solution greyish brown with Co and brown with Ni. The complex of Fe and other complexes resembled those with the above reagents. Complete precipitation of Ag and Hg^{II} became apparant.

Thiolactic p-chloroanilide, at p_n 3.42-7, gave white precipitate with Ag, Hg^{II} , Cd, As, Sb; yellow with MoO_4^{2-} , Pb at p_n 3.42-4, Bi at p_n 3.42-4; grey with Hg^I ; greyish violet with Cu; brown with Co at p_n 4-7; dark brown with Ni at p_n 5-7. In ammoniacal solution a deep brown precipitate with Co and pink coloration with Ni were observed. The behaviour of Fe and nature of the other complexes resembled the corresponding complexes of the above reagents. The precipitation with Ag and Hg^{II} appeared complete but the silver complex turned black on heating or keeping.

Sensitivity Tests.—Sensitivity tests for cobalt and nickel were made using the above thiolactic anilides. Tests for cobalt was carried out in ammoniacal solutions, while that for nickel was made in presence of a little of sodium acetate in which case the reagents were found to be more sensitive. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Reagent No.	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
For Co.						
PL ...	1:10 ³	1:10 ²	1:10 ³	1:10 ³	1:10 ³	1:10 ³
CL ...	1:10 ^{5.3}	1:10 ^{5.3}	1:10 ^{5.3}	1:10 ^{5.6}	1:10 ^{5.3}	1:10 ^{5.3}
For Ni.						
PL ...	1:10 ⁴					
CL ...	1:10 ⁵	1:10 ^{5.6}	1:10 ^{5.3}	1:10 ^{5.3}	1:10 ⁵	1:10 ^{5.3}

PL stands for 'precipitation limit', and CL for 'coloration limit'.

On comparing the above results with those obtained with the thioglycollanilides (*loc. cit.*) it is seen that thiolactic anilides are more sensitive for nickel than thioglycollanilides. This probably is due to the presence of a methyl group in the ring of chelation. Thus it opens up the possibility for the present series of reagents to be useful in the analysis of nickel.

Composition of Nickel Complexes.—The composition of the nickel complex of thiolactic *o*-toluidide was determined as follows. The complex was prepared by slow addition of an alcoholic solution of the reagent with stirring to a dilute solution of

NiSO_4 containing sodium acetate and acetic acid, just sufficient for a weak acidification. The mixture was digested on a water-bath for about an hour, filtered, and the precipitate washed well with hot water and then with alcohol to remove any excess of the reagent. The complex was dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . A known amount of the complex was ignited to NiO in a porcelain crucible from which the percentage of nickel was found to be 13.15% against the calculated value of 13.14% assuming Ni : reagent as 1 : 2 in the molecule of the complex. The probable structure for the complex, taking co-ordination number for Ni to be 4, is therefore

Other nickel complexes would have similar structures as they belong to the same group.

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